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Research Article

**DENTAL CLINICAL ANALYSIS: COMPARISON OF
VARIOUS DENTAL PROBLEMS BETWEEN MALE AND
FEMALE CHILDREN AND ADULTS****Sana Sharaf Uddin Shah¹, Fida Hussain², Sana Shah³, Wasfa Rasheed⁴,
Hadiqa Yousaf⁵, Iram Jamil⁶**¹BDS, M.Sc. (Operative Dentistry), Senior Registrar, Department of Dental Material,
Muhammad Dental College, Mirpurkhas, Sindh, Pakistan .²BDS, MDS, Assistant Professor, Oral and Maxillofacial Department, Bhattai Medical and
Dental College, MirpurKhas, Sindh.³BDS, FCPS trainee(Orthodontics), Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences,
Jamshoro⁴BDS, Lecturer operative dentistry, Liaquat College of medical and dentistry, Jamshoro⁵BDS, Dental Surgeon, Hyderabad, Sindh⁶MBBS, MCPS trainee (Pediatrics), General practitioner, Hyderabad, Sindh**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Dental health is of great importance due to multiple reasons as this region of the body is in frequent contact with the majority of disease causative agents. Apparently, all dental diseases seem to be equally affecting both genders and age groups so we conducted this research work to compare the various common dental cases between males and females as well as adults and children. There 1387 patient in total 816 (58.83%) were females and 571(41.17%) were males, 203(14.64%) were children and 1184(85.36%) were children. Dental Caries, Periodontitis, Oral ulcers and sub-mucosal fibrosis were almost equally distributed in males, females, children and adults no significant difference was seen on statistical analysis carried on chi-square p-values 0.2 and 0.12 respectively.

Conclusion: Dental diseases are equally affecting males, females, adults and children no statistical difference exists in between

Key Words: Dental caries, periodontitis, fibrosis, oral ulcers

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INTRODUCTION:

Dental caries is the localized destruction of susceptible dental hard tissue by acidic by-products from bacterial fermentation of dietary carbohydrates. It is a multi-factorial, dynamic and infectious microbiologic disease process resulting from imbalance in the physiologic equilibrium between the tooth mineral and the plaque liquid. The demineralization and remineralization processes go side by side and demineralization can be arrested at any point in time [1]. Mineral loss and consequent cavity formation is a result of imbalance in the dynamic equilibrium between tooth mineral and plaque fluid. In unfavorable conditions, the remineralization rate does not sufficiently neutralize the rate of demineralization and caries occurs [2,3]. Children show a high rate prevalence for dental caries as a common public global issue [4]. The quality of children life has much been affected by dental pain, dental loss in early life followed malnutrition as well as reduced child growth [5]. The prevalence rates in India for dental caries are reported to be between 51% to 54.1% [6,7]. The plaque is caused by lack of dental hygiene, age and gender effects, tooth-brushing abnormal habits with high intake of sugar containing drinks [8]. This study was aimed at analyzing the commonly presenting dental cases in terms of their frequency in male and female genders as well as on comparing these cases between adults and children.

METHODOLOGY:

Patients were registered in this study through non-probability, consecutive sampling with no age

limits and both genders were included. The only exclusion criterion was the follow up cases. Frequency and percentage was determined for various diseases and compared on SPSS version 22 using chi-square keeping 0.05 as level of significance.

RESULTS:

There were 816 (58.83%) females and 571(41.17%) males with a total of 1387 patients visiting the dental care hospital OPD over two month time period. Dental caries was the most common presentation 904(65.18%) both in male and female patients 355(25.59%) and 549(39.58%) respectively. Periodontitis patients were 392(28.26%) with 177(12.76%) as males and 215(15.50%), there were 73 (5.26%) Oral ulcers cases out of which 31(2.24%) were males and 42(3.03%) were females. Patients with sub-mucosal fibrosis were 8(0.58%) where males were 10 (0.72%) and females were 18(1.29%) when compared these chi-square there was non-significant difference between the two genders p-value 0.256[Table-1]. Dental Caries was the most common dental disease both in children 138(9.95%) as well as in adults 766(55.23%), similarly Periodontitis was the 2nd common most condition in children 47(3.39%) and adults 345(24.87%). Oral ulcers observed in children were 16(1.15%) and these were 57(4.11%) in adults whereas sub-mucosal fibrosis was least common in children 02(0.14%) as well as in adult group 16(1.15%) again non-significant difference was observed between the children and adults p-value 0.12[Table-2]

Table-1: Distribution and comparison various dental cases between males and females

Diseases	Male	Females	Row Total	X ²	P-value
Dental Caries	355(25.59%)	549(39.58%)	904(65.18%)	4.04	0.256
Periodontitis	177(12.76%)	215(15.50%)	392(28.26%)		
Oral ulcers	31(2.24%)	42(3.03%)	73 (5.26%)		
sub-mucosal fibrosis	8(0.58%)	10(0.72%)	18(1.29%)		
Total	571(41.17%)	816(58.83%)	1387(100%)		

Figure-1: Bar charts of comparison various dental cases between males and females

Table-2: Distribution and comparison various dental cases between children and adults

Diseases	Children	Adults	Row Total	X ²	P-Value
Dental Caries	138(9.95%)	766(55.23%)	904(65.18%)	5.76	0.12
Periodontitis	47(3.39%)	345(24.87%)	392(28.26%)		
Oral ulcers	16(1.15%)	57(4.11%)	73(5.26%)		
sub-mucosal fibrosis	02(0.14%)	16(1.15%)	18(1.29%)		
Total	203(14.64%)	1184(85.36%)	1387(100%)		

Figure-II: Bar charts of comparison various dental cases b/w children and adults

Figure-III: Pie charts of frequency of children and adults

DISCUSSION:

There were 816 (58.83%) females and 571(41.17%) males the current study which is consistent with the finding reported by Amir AK et al (2015) that were female 52% and male 48% [9]. Similarly Singh SK et al(2014)[10] as well as reports from Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan also showed dental caries higher among females in comparison to males Shaikh IA et al(2014)[11]. A study from India by Maru AM et al (2012) showed a non-significant difference between the two genders [12]. Contrasting results were published by Badar et al (2012)[13] and Shaikh et al(2014) who found 55.33% males while 44.66% females in his study[14]. We found periodontitis as 28% which is consistent with the reported global prevalence of periodontal diseases 20-50% in developed as well as developing nations [15]. The prevalence of periodontitis in Pakistan was reported to be 18% that was bit lower than what we found in the current study [16]. The world estimated prevalence for oral ulcers was reported as 4% the current study also found consistent figures to that one[17]. Dental diseases have been so common worldwide in both genders and all age groups which seem to be resulting from eating habits and poor oral hygiene. Modified life style and eating styles and oral hygiene is promoted the oral health can be improved in all communities round the globe leading to prevention of the associated systemic diseases as well.

CONCLUSION:

Dental cases were equally distributed male and female genders as well as children and adults with no significant difference in between

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